

Experts Speak

ANALYSING THE IMPACTS OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC

Concept Note

COVID-19 (Coronavirus Disease 2019) did not discriminate anyone based on their economy, political affiliation, power equation, or social strata. The virus has touched every continent and almost all the countries and impacted the entire humanity. Starting from the Wuhan city of central China from the middle of November 2019, it spread so fast that by the time people realised its vulnerability it had already engulfed all. On 30 January 2020 it was termed as 'Public Health Emergency of International Concern' and on 11 March 2020, it was recognized as a 'Pandemic'.

The Experts Speak section of the journal attempts to bring to fore some pertinent social-economic-strategic as well as psychological impacts of the pandemic on the entire humanity. As the pandemic is still upswing and the entirety of its impact is yet to be fully visible, the discussion analyses some repercussions so far. **Professor Nigam Dave** and **Raviraj Dave** explains the cascading effects of COVID-19 across economic and social sectors of India. The authors prescribe for a better response mechanism to such crisis if ever arise in future through resilient leadership and collaboration across various sectors. A focused analysis is advanced by **Dr. Nausheen Nizami** on the impact of Covid-19 pandemic on India's macroeconomic sector - especially the macroeconomic constraints behind the fiscal and monetary stimulus packages announced by the Indian Government and the challenges that pose to the economy in mitigating such crisis. Dr Nizami points out that the biggest fiscal challenge amidst Covid-19 crisis for India is: how to effectively revive and accelerate the economic growth rate to above six per cent in the next two financial years. As she suggests, the current situation warrants for a comprehensive strategy of reviving all the industries in the primary, secondary and tertiary sector.

On the other hand, **Dr Arbind Sinha** examines the ground realities through the social lens by scrutinising the impacts of the pandemic on the lives people. Aptly the author argues that though it is not wrong that the pandemic has affected all layers of society, yet a minute study would reveal that it has a differential bearing on each section and sub-section of the society. The rural Indians, urban Indians, the labourers - though all have suffered enormously, the resilience of each strata is not same, therefore the impact is differential: different social strata have suffered differently. **Dr Sitakanta Mishra** takes the debate to the global level and argues that the geopolitical implications of COVID-19 pandemic are undoubtedly secondary compared to the global health and safety concerns; but in long-run, the upshot of the pandemic would be consequential for the global order in vogue. In the wake of pandemic, a global power vacuum has emerged given the fact that all major powers consumed with internal problems have become inward looking for fighting the pandemic. Dr Mishra argues that the upshot of the COVID-19 would certainly be consequential for the current world order; the world may gradually inch towards a new world order with new set of power equations and structural adjustments. He asserts that if the US and European powers remain absent in shaping a global unity to deal with the pandemic as they used to until now on other occasions, China and India may use the crisis as an opportunity to start setting new rules and initiate actions according to their global governance visions.

Lastly, **Gitanjali Sinha Roy** examines how the 'China threat' is a common factor in India-Japan strategic relations which is likely to strengthen in the atmosphere of COVID-19 pandemic. Chinese aggressiveness with respect to India and Japan is in fact propelling convergence of interests between New Delhi and Tokyo which would lead to greater collaboration among them, and also among their regional partners, culminating in an intra-Asian forum in future.